

Theoretical reflection and concepts in urban historical research. The Barrio of Chepinque, Zacatecas, Mexico, a case study

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Abstract

The historical heritage in Mexico is a subject little addressed and even less understood, because various problems arise with respect to the way in which the theories and methodologies that allow us to have the appropriate dynamics to be in conditions to interpret all the information that is presented to us, in order to clarify the dynamics by which the different urban centers and buildings have undergone modifications over the centuries.

That is why one of the main objectives of this paper is to show a theoretical reflection, as well as all those concepts that are used in order to strengthen the results obtained from research in the area of the humanities, since historical settlements are usually variable and complex objects of study. The cities as containers of facts and social actions, offer different possibilities with which they can be understood and analyzed, their architectural, historical and urban characteristics must be taken into account as a whole and not as separate entities.

Key words: Heritage, historical and urban archaeology, theoretical concepts and methodological approaches.

Introduction

The importance of historical, architectural and urban research lies in the implementation of the precepts offered by *Urban History*, which leads us to historical documentary research, the analysis of architectural changes and urban reconditioning, as well as archaeological exploration, with the purpose of understanding the different processes of conformation and permanence of urban space. Due to the complexity of this type of settlement, one of the theoretical positions that is appropriate to form a *corpus* of concepts and techniques is called urban history, an approach that proposes various ideas and precepts that help us interpret the context.

This study is based on the need to delve into the analysis of the architectural solutions, which occurred at the different times in which the site was developed, to resolve various factors, such as the irregular topography of the land on which people wanted to place the buildings,¹ the climate² and the channels of the streams,³

¹ The circumstances of the foundation and the characteristics of the land largely defined the layout of the architectural plant, for example, a prison, outpost or royal mine, did not have the same urban layout conditions as a city previously projected according to the laws and regulations, this is ruled in the Ordinances issued by Carlos V in 1526, "*Do not choose places to settle in very high areas due to the inconvenience of the winds and difficulty of service and hauling, nor in very low places, because they are usually sick, merge into the moderately raised ones, that enjoy the north and midday winds uncovered...*". Cortés Rocha, Xavier, "Los orígenes del urbanismo novohispano" en *Revista Omnia*, 1988, p.23.

² One of the aspects that was considered when choosing the place where the city would be built was the climate, which determined not only the location and spatial orientation of the buildings, but also the dimensions of the streets, these ideas were picked up by Diego Sagredo in 1526 from Vitruvio's great treatise on architecture. Element that was included in the *Ordenanza* No. 40 of the group of Discovery and Population Ordinances signed by Felipe II in 1573, all this to ensure good health conditions. Castro Orellana, Rodrigo, "Ciudades de Sísifo. Urbanismo Colonial y Contingencia" en *Revista Estudios Avanzados*, número 26, 2017, pp.118-119; Hardoy, Jorge, "La Forma de las Ciudades Coloniales en Hispanoamerica" en *Revista de Indias*, 1973, p. 1.

³ One of the main activities that took place during the planning period of the cities was the use of water, since without the presence of the vital liquid, populations could not exist, so the success and growth of a city was the correct conduction of the streams, so that they do not generate overflow or sanitary problems and that people could benefit from the water for their services, whether domestic or industrial.

For the beginnings of the New Spain cities, the aforementioned was an important element, which was described in some regulations and treaties, such is the case of the treaty called *Lo Crestià* (1385-1392) by Francesc Eiximenic, which establishes that "*the propitious place for the construction of the city, it must be on a wide plain for its expansion with abundant sources of water*", for his part, León Batista Alberti, in his work *De re aedificatoria* suggested "*...avoid stagnant or muddy waters, which would be breeding grounds of mosquitoes, worms and diseases...*". In 1597, Jaime Castillo de Bovadilla, made reference to the care of the

conditions required to found the cities in New Spain. As Carlos Chanfón mentions, it is necessary to "...scrutinize the origins of the urban layout...",⁴ which will allow us to have the necessary information to assimilate that the layout of the buildings "...is anchored to cultural, religious, social and economic reasons...",⁵ which determined its constant architectural and urban changes.

It is then those concepts such as interdisciplinarity, permanence, use of plans, modernity, among others, were implemented in a specific urban environment such as the Barrio Chepinque located in the city of Zacatecas, Mexico. It allowed to make an accumulation of musings regarding the little historical information that is available about that area, despite the variety of documentary sources that exist and the new results of the interdisciplinary work carried out by archaeologists, historians, architects and engineers.⁶ The aforementioned professional approach was decisive for the choice of this project, since, at that time, it was not possible to answer a series of questions and elucidations about the origin, transformation and permanence of this area, which housed spaces of strong social interaction, themselves that had different functions, from religious, economic, recreational and residential.

The archaeological and historical explorations allow us to reflect on all those buildings that remain hidden; as well as the cultural objects that define society at different times, which requires our attention to decipher how an urban space is transformed according to the different projects implemented by local institutions and elites, as well as by society as a whole.

From our position, we believe that in order to be able to analyze urban transformation, architectural change, land use modification and the correlation between architecture and urbanism with urban symbolic processes, it must be

works of the city, emphasizing the need to control the water and the care of the streets. Suárez García, Carlos, "El urbanismo humanista y la policía española" en *Revista Topoi*, volumen 16, 2015, pp. 141-145.

⁴ Chanfón Olmos, Carlos (coordinador), *Historia de la arquitectura y el urbanismo mexicanos*, Vol. II El Periodo Virreinal, Tomo II El Proceso de Consolidación de la Vida Virreinal, 1997, p. 15.

⁵ *Idem*.

⁶ Montoya Ortega, Efrén, "Caracterización del Espacio Urbano Novohispano. El barrio de Chepinque de la ciudad de Zacatecas" en *Estudios sobre Zacatecas. Arte, cultura y urbanismo II*, 2023, p. 1.

approached from a process of historical permanence,⁷ taking into account the different disciplinary views that contribute to the analysis of our object of study, considering all the stages of changes, reconditioning and construction phases.

1. Conceptualization of the built urban space

The New Spain city is the urban settlement created or conceived in a specific period of time, ranging from the 16th to the 19th century; It is the result of the implementation of a series of institutions or organizations of a public or semi-public nature, with a social structure that operates them. It is a built environment whose purpose is to contain and manage a series of activities that provide goods and services to the people who inhabit them, satisfying their fundamental needs, in a manner recognized and authorized by the prevailing State.⁸ These inhabited environments, as well as the specific elements⁹ that make it up, are complex and variable objects of study that preserve the cultural, social and material redoubts of the human groups that built it.¹⁰

They are the reflection of the needs and solutions that were proposed to appropriate nature itself, conditioning the landscapes with the ultimate goal of subsisting over time. That is to say, it is the way in which the Spanish conquistador arranged himself on this new landscape in which he lived. The way in which he scattered his homes in nature and how he placed the buildings belonging to community life. These establishments reflect the natural environment, the level of

⁷ Cities and their specific spaces, such as neighborhoods, neighborhoods, plazas, streets, alleys and buildings, are omnipresent manifestations of societies, which have a continuity and recurrence as a built and planned cultural-historical product, which is also lasting since changes between social systems do not necessarily end the built place, so they have to be studied for long periods of time to clarify this functionality and the reasons why it was transformed over time. Mejía Pavony, Germán Rodrigo, *Los Años del Cambio: Historia Urbana de Bogotá 1820-1910*, 2000, pp. 15-16.

⁸ These places are the vestiges of years of planning and execution, which legitimized the intellectual power of the Spanish Crown. Camacho Cardona, Mario, *Historia Urbana Novohispánica del Siglo XVI*, 2009, p. 12-13.

⁹ We refer to characteristic spaces, be it a neighborhood, a street, a particular building, or a series of them, the urban equipment, the construction material, etc.

¹⁰ Montoya Ortega, Efrén, *Op. cit.*, pp. 8-9.

technology at which the builders operated, and various institutions of social interaction and control that the culture maintained.¹¹ They are the footprint, the trail that man has left behind, which helps us to conceive his passage through history, his vision of the world according to the temporality they occupied, his perception of the context in which it developed.

1.1 Interdiscipline in the urban context of New Hispanic cities

As previously established, interdisciplinarity has been the main concept with which urban history promotes exegesis about the building space, so interdisciplinarity is defined as "[...] the creation of comprehensive knowledge that starts from different sources, but that in the end remains constituted by only one."¹² On the other hand, within the urban history agenda, interdisciplinarity is one of the primary precepts, with James Dyos being the one who from the British school suggested that when studying topics related to the urban, they should be carried out through various methodologies and theories that they emanate from other sciences or disciplines, which will contribute to the problematization of the physical areas to be observed.¹³

Dyos encouraged the use of interdisciplinarity within urban history and as well as its multiple visions:

[...] urban history, it should be clear, is a field of knowledge, not a single discipline in the accepted sense, but a field in which many disciplines converge, or at least is based on this. In practice, this meant that urban history comprised a relatively small congregation of avid congregants, but that its sphere of influence drew widely from different faiths.¹⁴

¹¹ Willey, Gordon, *Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Perú*, 1953. p. 25.

¹² Manzanilla, Linda, *et. al.*, "La interdisciplina en arqueología: Propuestas desde la UNAM" en *Revista de la Universidad de México*, no. 627, pp. 5-16, 2003.

¹³ Miranda Pacheco, Sergio, "La Historia Urbana en México, Crítica de una Historiografía Inexistente" en Quiroz Rothe, Héctor y Esther Maya Pérez (compiladores) *Urbanismo. Temas y Tendencias*, 2012, p. 352.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 358.

What mattered was the interest in the whole of the city and its connections to the broader context rather than the specific methodological approach being taken. Dyos later commented that, although urban history had lost its irregularity during the 1970s, thanks to the emergence of a more coherent scholarly identity through its lectures, periodicals, and book series, "it would be a rude presumption to pretend who somehow had a distinctive discipline."¹⁵

But it is not only about introducing the methodologies of various sciences to address this issue, interdiscipline promotes the generation of knowledge at a cognitive level by integrating the information obtained, it must be achieved

[...] analysis within each of the participating disciplines, to subsequently jointly arrive at a synthesis of each of its parts and thereby make an evaluation of the knowledge created while it is being integrated. Data analysis, within the disciplines, implies opening the doors to discussion, since a cognitive level has already been reached where comparison, criticism and analysis itself are viable. When the working group interacts with a package of information at this level, it is possible to organize, compare and evaluate it, to later synthesize and build it as integrated knowledge.¹⁶

The evolution of the humanistic sciences and the variability of the built context have pushed academics to modify certain criteria on the topics of their respective investigations, history is not only made by itself, other approaches are also involved to reinforce interpretations. and avoid leaving aside aspects that may be vital in the investigations. The same that can be so disparate but that actually contribute to the field of knowledge.

Cities and their specific spaces, such as *barrios*, neighborhoods, squares, streets, alleys, and buildings, are ubiquitous manifestations of societies, which have continuity and recurrence as a built and planned cultural-historical product, which is also long-lasting since changes between social systems do not necessarily end the

¹⁵ Ewen, Shane, *What is Urban History?*, 2016., p. 22.

¹⁶ Manzanilla, Linda, *et. al.*, *Op. Cit.*, p. 7.

built place, so they have to be studied for long periods of time to clarify this functionality and the reasons why it was transformed over time.¹⁷

1.2 Permanence or persistence in the historical urban settlement

Being a specific built space within the city of Zacatecas, temporalities have to be observed in the sense of permanence, that is, these significant changes over long periods of time, since specific social events are not studied, but rather modifications in the architectural structure. In this way, we will approach the building transformation process in the Barrio Chepinque, using the Porfirian house owned by General Jesús Aréchiga as a case study.¹⁸ Given this panorama, we will take the theoretical postulates of the French school of urban history, proposed by Bedarida, which establish that:

[...] the urban phenomenon cannot be understood unless said phenomenon is returned to its place at the heart of a millennial movement, since urban societies, as well as urban forms, are rooted in a distant past.¹⁹

Urban history investigates "the urban presence in the broader society",²⁰ which allows control of the different variables to offer better results in the analysis. Likewise, *the theory of permanence and the monuments* promoted by Poëte and Lavedan from the French school are taken into account, where the following can be reasoned:

The persistences or permanences are noticed through the monuments, the physical signs of the past, but also through the persistence of the layouts and the plane. [...] the cities remain on axes of development, they maintain the position of their layouts,

¹⁷ Mejía Pavony, Germán Rodrigo, *Op. Cit.*, p. 56.

¹⁸ Montoya Ortega, Efrén, *Op. Cit.*, pp. 10-11.

¹⁹ Bedarida, Francois, "The French approach to Urban History. An Assessment of Recent Methodological Trends", cited in Mejía Pavony, Germán Rodrigo, *Op. Cit.*, p. 23.

²⁰ Guardia, Manuel, *et. al.*, "Los Atlas de las Ciudades entre la Descripción y la Comparación", in Sambricio, Carlos (editor), *La Historia Urbana. Revista Ayer*, nº 23, 1996, p. 110.

they grow according to the direction and with the meaning of events older than the current ones, often remote.²¹

Trying to reason and delve into the permanence of buildings or neighborhood complexes, is a practice that can lead us to explain the constant unknowns represented by the erected heritage, which can make us aware of that "past that we still experience".²² That is to say, what is proposed as permanence or persistence is that past-present relationship.

The most significant permanence is thus given by the streets and by the plane; the plan remains under various levels, differs in terms of attributions, often deforms, but substantially does not change location.²³

For Lavedan, persistence becomes the generatrix of the plane; This generatrix is the main objective of urban disquisitions because, with its understanding, it is possible to go back to the spatial formation of the city; in the generatrix it encompasses the concept of persistence that also extends to physical buildings, streets, and urban monuments.²⁴

Let us exemplify this concept, is the Aréchiga house a permanent building? In this case, permanence is not applied due to the simple fact that the form of the past is still experienced in this building, that the physical form of the past has assumed varied functions and has continued to function, albeit with variations, conditioning that urban contour and constituting always an important focus of it.²⁵ Somehow, this house is currently used, although obviously its function has changed radically, it is no longer a home, it is now a learning space, but it is still present in the neighborhood and forms a conclusive part of its structure.²⁶

²¹ Rossi, Aldo, *La arquitectura de la ciudad*, 2007., p. 99.

²² *Ibidem*, 98.

²³ *Ídem*.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 87.

²⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 101.

²⁶ Here, the form of the past has assumed a different function, but it is intimately in the city, it has been modified, and it is correct to think that it could still be changed. *Ibidem*, p. 102.

The dynamic process of the city tends towards evolution than conservation, and that in evolution the monuments are preserved and represent events that promote the same development.²⁷

All this can be appreciated in our object of study, this space since the 19th century has been the target of numerous modifications that tend to transformation or modernity, despite that, reuse was a constant, despite that apparently a systematic destruction of the urban context was carried out, vestiges or reminiscences were left.

To interpret the contexts, historical-urban archeology uses written sources, plans, maps, lithographs and photographs that together make it possible to interpret the architectural contexts that make up a defined universe of study, individually or jointly. This type of archeology has the functionality of contributing to the conceptualization and methodological application to understand the idea of the city, without distinction of periods, from its origins to its most recent history.²⁸ This approach allows us to observe it as an identifiable socio-spatial object that has its own materiality, which is the product of an organized human group, which has a collective conscience.²⁹

In Mexico, the urban development of cities is approached by historical-urban archeology where its objective is both the building itself and the content of the subsoil, this allows, on the one hand, to obtain new data on the properties, locating areas and using a stratigraphic analysis of historical constructions where the numerous construction units that make up a building, a block or an urban sector can be identified and analyzed,³⁰ which helps to think about its systemic context. However, since these are holistic studies, it must not be forgotten that they tend

²⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 104.

²⁸ *Ídem*

²⁹ Monnet, Jérôme, "Del Urbanismo a la Urbanidad: Un Diálogo entre Geografía y Arqueología sobre la Ciudad", in Sanders, William T., *et. al.* (edit.) *El Urbanismo en Mesoamérica*, 2005, p. 21-42.

³⁰ Azkarate Garai-Olaun, Agustín e Iñaki García Camino, "La Ciudad, Documento Histórico: Reflexiones sobre la práctica de la arqueología urbana en la comunidad autónoma del País Vasco", in KOBIE (Serie Paleoantropología), núm. XXIII, 1996, p. 141.

towards integration where the present processes will always be dynamic at different moments in their history. In the words of Litvak King:

[...] the city, constantly renewing itself, finds that its older parts are of no use to it. [...] the urban dynamics and the parts that were dedicated to one activity have to be adapted to another. Fashions have changed, and the styles that were popular at one time must be replaced by others. The city grows and the old parts must change with it or become fossilized. When this occurs, the city destroys itself, and in doing so cannibalizes itself. New buildings are built. For this purpose, some are destroyed and thus, the new building remains on top of the older part.³¹

With the above, it is clear that there must be a general overview of the transformations of the built structures and it must be estimated that the constructions must be individualized according to their constructive units and their articulation in a diachronic sequence, which allows characterizing the construction techniques of the different periods. These parts can be considered as phenomena of permanence or also known as persistence, a concept where they warn, through the monuments, the physical signs of the past, a situation that is highlighted through the continuation of the urban lines.³²

For each object of study there are specific approaches that allow understanding them; each researcher is supported by proposals, concepts, methodologies and theories that help to build the skeleton of the investigations. In the particular case of this work, being such a complex and variable topic, the theoretical-conceptual implications that are addressed have to be taken up again according to the systematic needs that arise. When trying to explain the urban construct, in previous paragraphs we spoke about a branch of history, which includes these events within the city, urban history and its precepts on multidisciplinary, the use of plans and the concept of permanence. This helps us to understand the space addressed, which corresponds to the Barrio Chepinque of the city of Zacatecas.

³¹ Litvak King, Jaime, *Todas las piedras tienen 2000 años*, 2000, pp. 65-67.

³² Rossi, Aldo, *Op. Cit.*, pp. 35-37.

Historical-urban archeology goes beyond combining methodologies that have to do with excavations in historical areas and the reading of documents that are usually stored in archives. In Mexico, archaeological work is traditionally reserved for pre-Hispanic contexts, it refers especially to the subsoil and ancestral materials of which, in most cases, there are no documentary records with which to verify the assertions that are issued. However, there are specialty areas within archeology that explore currently inhabited areas, spaces with a relatively recent chronology, which have texts in which historical memories are stored.

It is in this way that urban-historical archeology is conceptualized within the epistemology of modernity, this means exploring different perspectives on the processes that have shaped this condition, as well as the way in which the past is understood. from a present perspective. Urban-historical archeology tries to understand processes rather than focusing on an era or a condition.³³

1.3 Importance of the use of plans in the understanding of urban configuration

In such a case, what is a blueprint or a plane? How does it help us to observe urban changes? What kind of information can we appreciate? As a glossary, we can understand, in a few words, that a plan is the graphic manifestation of the characteristics of a city,³⁴ they were and are usually made by the administrative authorities, in order to have control of urban growth, to spread the services to the population. These documents, used as chronological series, invite us to observe the spatial structures, the transitions of the buildings and the layout based on their urban character. In the plans we notice complex representations of the cities that we intend to address,

³³ Hall, Martin and Stephen W. Silliman, "Chapter I. Introduction: Archaeology of the Modern World" in Hall, Martin and Stephen W. Silliman (editors), *Historical Archaeology*, 2006, p. 2.

³⁴ These characteristics, geometric, spatial, urban, can be decisive for the functions that the inhabitants granted. Each building had a particular function within its own context, which varied depending on the conditions that nature offered, or the needs of its members.

[...] their disposition, which can be assigned (in case of creation) or adapted (in case of reuse) [...] this identification of urban space rests above all on the relatively important density of specific functional structures: multiplication of the open spaces that allow circulation in an agglomeration of closed spaces, the existence of extensive spaces that allow the gathering of crowds, the solidity of the constructions that support the permanence of the structures [...]³⁵

For urban history, the concept of plan becomes a multifactorial element, which can be used as a means of interpretation to observe the permanence and/or transformations of the built space, through the plan we can notice the widening of the streets, the appearance of new buildings, their changes, changes in land use and the disappearance of properties.

The study of the nineteenth-century city requires the elaboration of an idea of a plan sufficiently elastic and adjusted to reality to accept different types of city and allow the interpretation of urban realities [...]³⁶

A precept must be considered that has to do with knowledge of the city plan, which

[...] makes us reflect on the type of society that space has produced. Analyzing the plan of the city (the spatial organization, its morphological structure) brings us closer to the knowledge of the society that has generated it.³⁷

The layout of the buildings within a defined layout can be isolated through the graphic concepts embodied in a plan or map; these instruments can be used to complement the information obtained from the inquiries. For the historian, a map is nothing more than a general and visual description of the area he is inspecting, however, for the purposes of our work, the maps we have are part of the essential *corpus* itself that will be implemented to expand the interpretation spectrum.³⁸

³⁵ Monnet, Jérôme, *Op. Cit.*, p. 27.

³⁶ Piñón, Juan Luis, "Apreciaciones sobre los márgenes de la historia urbana" en Sambricio, Carlos (editor), in *La Historia Urbana. Revista Ayer*, nº 23, 1996, pp. 17-18.

³⁷ Rossi, Aldo, *Op. Cit.*, p. 99.

³⁸ Montoya Ortega, Efrén, *Op. Cit.*, p. 12

By virtue of the traces, the reconstruction of the plan of the ancient city appears as the primary goal to be achieved. Even more than historians, archaeologists pay constant attention to the physical city. The reconstructed plan, based on information from all sources, is the condensed expression of our knowledge. What's more, it contains the truth. It has the virtue of being the objective expression of known reality, probably incomplete, however, authentic, concrete, palpable and irrefutable.³⁹

The morphology of the city is made up of the plan, the buildings and the land uses. For these purposes, the plan is a graphic-documentary instrument that offers information which can be decoded by separating the embodied elements, disaggregating each of the representations of the buildings to facilitate a reconstruction of the plan in the transcendental stages. The built space reflects the arrangement of the buildings in a plan and the way in which it can be read is through the plans, because indeed the city, through the plans can be read as a text, it is a palimpsest that Like a manuscript, it preserves traces of a previous writing, parts that are erased and rewritten or reused can be seen, but traces always remain.⁴⁰

Conclusions

Being an object of study that deals with building elements, postulates from sciences and related disciplines had to be taken. To begin with, all those theoretical positions that served as the scaffolding or skeleton of the investigations were raised, in this vein, the elaboration of the state of the question contributed to the articulation of the knowledge that exists around the study of cities, specifically of the New Spain Barrio Chepinque of the city of Zacatecas, as well as the theoretical-methodological concepts that were used throughout the investigation, once several currents of thought were reviewed, it was decided to make use of what is known as Urban History, since its propositions and premises, were adapted to the theme and the objectives set.

³⁹ Galinié, Henri, *Ciudad, Espacio Urbano y Arqueología, La Fábrica Urbana*, 2012, pp. 35-36.

⁴⁰ Capel, Horacio, *La Morfología de las Ciudades. Tomo I: Sociedad, Cultura y Paisaje Urbano*, 2002, p. 70.

It is Urban History that precisely proposes multidisciplinary for studies as complex as cities and their components. With which it seeks to create comprehensive knowledge that uses disparate proposals. With this methodological idea, it is based on the premise that each material associated with any finding must be studied under analytical thinking -not only descriptive-, and that each science or discipline involved has free access to all the necessary documentation sources.

It is then that, thanks to this position, concepts such as permanence were used, which are the temporalities that have to be observed, that is, these significant changes over long periods of time, since concrete social facts are not studied, but rather the modifications in the architectural structure. Said permanence can be seen reflected precisely in the settlement pattern of the object of study, since they have received different treatments throughout the centuries, even losing on some occasions the original land use for which they were built; This permanence is reflected in the construction systems detected throughout the excavations, in what we could define as an interesting reuse of the raw material.

On the other hand, one of the activities that can be considered as purely technical and that for the most part is only used to provide a geographical context, is the use of graphic documentation, referring to plans, maps, sketches, photographs, in this case, they were useful to interpret the origin, transformation and expansion of this space, through the scale representation of the houses and the structures of a religious and industrial nature. That is, the concept of plan becomes a multifactorial element, which can be used as a means of interpretation to observe the permanence and/or transformations of the built space, through the plan we can notice the widening of the streets, the appearance of new buildings, their changes, changes in land use and the disappearance of properties.

The drawings of the houses, the temples and the mines, help to understand the way in which the authors perceived their environment, depending on the technique and the way in which they were captured, lucubrations can be made

regarding that aspect of modernity,⁴¹ the way in which the structures were dispersed and even, supported by archival information, the raw materials used in the manufacture of the buildings can be deciphered.

Other relevant concepts are, for example, modernity, which are transitions given by certain social, economic, and political events that promote a change in manufacturing and in the systems in which all the buildings in the immediate environment are built. In the same way, the destruction of certain places is given by necessity to that modernity, which makes the inhabitants observe how certain buildings are unnecessary and dangerous within the urban fabric, wanting to give it a view that for a time can be considered as better.

Specifically, the area or urban settlement that was the interest of this work, is located in a portion of the city of Zacatecas, on this population, various investigations have been focused, mainly concentrating their attention on the events that happened in the buildings that make up the streets. and the *barrios*.⁴² As mentioned, it is that these theoretical precepts such as permanence, continuities and modernity have been relevant in understanding the built environment within a given area.

⁴¹ Modernity must be considered as an obligatory reference for the criticism of the current architectural situation, the characteristics of said modernity must be investigated first. It has been seen that the break with the humanist tradition is particularly reflected in architecture, as the rejection of traditional forms and the consequent need to carry out experimentation aimed at finding new forms. As a reaction to modernity, there has been a return to the figurativeness of traditional forms in an indiscriminate reuse of materials from history. Cortés, Juan Antonio, *Modernidad y Arquitectura, Una Idea Alternativa de Modernidad en el Arte Moderno*, 2003, p. 50.

⁴² We insist that it must be taken into account that the analysis of the *Barrio* undoubtedly corresponds to the same processes of formation of the metropolis, we must consider then that the neighborhoods in the case of Zacatecas, are not subordinate to each other, but rather are parts relatively autonomous; their relationships cannot be explained with a simple dependency function, but must be related to the entire urban structure. *Ídem*.

References

- Azkarate Garai-Olaun, Agustín e Iñaki García Camino, “La Ciudad, Documento Histórico: Reflexiones sobre la práctica de la arqueología urbana en la comunidad autónoma del País Vasco”, en *KOBIE* (Serie Paleoantropología), núm. XXIII, Bizkaiko Foru Aldundia-Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, Bilbao, 1996, p.141-161. Retrieved from http://www.bizkaia.eus/fitxategiak/04/Kobie/PDF/2/KOBIE_23_LA%20CIUDAD,%20DOCUMENTO%20HIST%3%93RICO_REFLEXIONES%20S OBRE%20L.pdf?hash=72448e1dcc7529efd947ea7a8f4ee879, in October, 2018.
- Camacho Cardona, Mario, *Historia Urbana Novohispánica del siglo XVI*, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Facultad de Estudios Superiores Acatlán, México, 2009.
- Capel, Horacio, *La Morfología de las Ciudades. Tomo I: Sociedad, Cultura y Paisaje Urbano*, Ediciones del Serbal, 2002.
- Castro Orellana, Rodrigo, “Ciudades de Sísifo. Urbanismo Colonial y Contingencia” en *Revista Estudios Avanzados*, número 26, Madrid, España, 2017, pp. 114-129. Retrieved from <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=5774032>, in October, 2019.
- Cortés, Juan Antonio, “Modernidad y Arquitectura, Una Idea Alternativa de Modernidad en el Arte Moderno”, in *Arquitectura Bis*, no. 36, 2003, pp. 48-54.
- Cortés Rocha, Xavier, “Los orígenes del urbanismo novohispano” en *Revista Omnia*, Coordinación General de Estudios de Posgrado, UNAM, 1988, pp. 20 – 35.

Retrieved from <https://studylib.es/doc/5528544/los-or%C3%ADgenes-del-urbanismo-novohispano.-xavier-cort%C3%A9s-rocha>, in March, 2020.

Chanfón Olmos, Carlos (coordinador), *Historia de la arquitectura y el urbanismo mexicanos, Vol. II El Periodo Virreinal, Tomo I El Encuentro de Dos Universos Culturales*, México, FCE, UNAM, 2001.

Ewen, Shane, *What is Urban History?*, Polity Press, Cambridge, UK, 2016.

Galinié, Henri, *Ciudad, Espacio Urbano y Arqueología, La Fábrica Urbana*, Universitat de València, 2012.

Guardia, Manuel; Francisco Javier Monclús y José Luis Oyón, “Los Atlas de Ciudades entre la Descripción y la Comparación. El Atlas Histórico de Ciudades Europeas” in Sambricio, Carlos (editor), *La Historia Urbana. Revista Ayer*, nº 23, 1996, pp. 109-134.

Hall, Martin and Stephen W. Silliman, “Chapter I. Introduction: Archaeology of the Modern World” in Hall, Martin and Stephen W. Silliman (editors), *Historical Archaeology*, Wiley-Blackwell, 2006, pp. 2-15.

Hardoy, Jorge, “La Forma de las Ciudades Coloniales en Hispanoamerica” en *Revista de Indias*, Tomo 33, Madrid, España, 1973, pp. 1-17. Retrieved from <https://catedrapernautfadu.files.wordpress.com/2015/06/ficha-bibliografica-nc2b08-la-forma-de-las-ciudades-coloniales.pdf>, in June, 2019.

Manzanilla, Linda, Emily McClung, Luis Barba y Raúl Valadez, “La interdisciplina en arqueología: Propuestas desde la UNAM” en *Revista de la Universidad de México*, no. 627, pp. 5-16, 2003. Retrieved from <https://f002.backblazeb2.com/file/rum-storage/e67778e5-39b8-481f-8e60-3608cf31e805.pdf>, in February, 2019.

Mejía Pavony, Germán Rodrigo, *Los años del cambio: historia urbana de Bogotá 1820-1910*, Bogotá, CEJA, 2000.

Miranda Pacheco, Sergio, “La Historia Urbana en México, Crítica de una Historiografía Inexistente” en Quiroz Rothe, Héctor y Esther Maya Pérez (compiladores) *Urbanismo. Temas y Tendencias*, 2012, p. 349-361. Retrieved from <https://leerlaciudadblog.files.wordpress.com/2016/05/miranda-la-historia-urbana-en-mc3a9xico-crc3adtica-de-una-historiografc3ada-inexistente.pdf>, in January, 2019.

Montoya Ortega, Efrén, “Caracterización del Espacio Urbano Novohispano. El barrio de Chepinque de la ciudad de Zacatecas” en *Estudios sobre Zacatecas. Arte, cultura y urbanismo II*, Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas, México, 2023, pp. 1-19.

Piñón, Juan Luis, “Apreciaciones sobre los márgenes de la historia urbana” in Sambricio, Carlos (editor), *La Historia Urbana*. Revista Ayer, nº 23, 1996, pp. 15-28.

Rossi, Aldo, *La arquitectura de la ciudad*, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, 2007.

Suárez García, Carlos José, “El urbanismo humanista y la "policía española" en el Nuevo Reino de Granada, siglo XVI” en *Revista Topoi*, volumen 16, número 30, Río de Janeiro, Brasil, 2015, pp. 125 – 156. Retrieved from <https://www.scielo.br/pdf/topoi/v16n30/2237-101X-topoi-16-30-00127.pdf> in November, 2019.

Willey, Gordon, *Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Perú*. Smithsonian Institution, Bureau of American Ethnology. Washington, USA, 1953.